

Between Dreaming and Waking:

Proust and the Reverberations of Associationism

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Proust wanders, between dreaming and waking, through complex associations that link states of consciousness, drawn from a storehouse imperfect recollections. In *The Search of lost Time*, it is the kiss of his mother, a tender affectionate moment, which brings to life a world of relations: impressions, sensations and associations. It is the act of tracing these relations that reveals something of their interdependencies: how one is moved when another is touched.

Tracing them allows a glimpse into human interiority. It opens a door through which one can perceive something of human nature. To trace ideas is to uncover the marks of life - habits, gestures, articulations - and how they reflect social standing, personal ambition, and, of course, vanity and pretence. They speak of the essence of taste, the substance of feeling, language, and music, and ultimately of the emergence of the self. For this reason, no distinction is made between art and life. In a sense, everything becomes a trace - a sign of emotional life and of the strategies devised to sustain it. Due to the act of tracery, it is not the logic of time and place that organises paragraphs, but the logic of the mind. The personal experience of memory and recall become the organizing principle behind the anachronistic order of events. The structuring principle is guided by the pathways between feelings, emotions and ideas.

It is a kiss that first introduces the concept of longing. But, it is the view of an old church at Combray, whose appearance seems to hold a kernel of thought. A thought dedicated, perhaps, to Ruskin whom Proust admired. Ruskin, who was “drunk on Gothic,” and trembled at the sight of the Gothic Cathedral of Saint-Urbain in Troyes.¹

Gothic architecture was, unlike classical architecture, able to function like a framework, build of small, almost semantic parts, to be read as a story. Gothic was structured, but somewhat fragmentary, like a collage and more than other styles it carried the signature of its craftsmen, of national character. Ruskin was a man, who was himself schooled in British empiricism, more precisely associationism. That doctrine that thought of mind, body and idea as bound in a causal chain, where one event influences another, from the outside to inside, and eventually back again. Ruskin, a man of his time, saw relationships between the world of things and the world of ideas. Gothic with its perceived ability to connect gave form to this quality.

1 Proust, “Ruskin” in Proust, *Days of Reading*, 1

Like Ruskin, and others, who traced associations between the landscape, human nature and architecture. Proust traces the residue of experience back to their origins, between past and present, as though following his own neurons and the connections sparked across different episodes of his life. To state the thesis more clearly: his entire exposition demonstrates the workings of associative memory - not merely of an ideal, logical or symbolic kind, but also of a nervously romantic one.²

But the traces seem to surpass the boundaries of a single mind, they are followed through society. Feeling, emotions and ideas arise not in isolation, but within a social context, in exchange with others. Proust's expositions on people, character and relationships within the context of commodities and artistic objects reveal not only something about the antagonists of his novel, but reach into the mechanisms of social formation. Exposing the dependency between the self and society.

Written at the end of the Fin de Siecle, which was itself aware that it marked the end as well as the beginning of an era, proust's work becomes a commentary on the rapid transformation of social conventions and symbolic exchange in the early twentieth century - a world charged with semiotic arousal and emotional reflexes.³

II

When Proust retraces his experiences through time, his method is not unique. He follows a preposition many had made before him, from empiricists to psychologists, aestheticians, pedagoges and artists. The preposition is that it is possible to trace thoughts and doing so uncovering something about yourself and the world.

Empiricist philosophers, such as Locke and Hume had traced ideas to the objective world around them in order to understand something about the order of things. In the same tradition, at the cusp of Romanticism, Archibald Alison suggested that emotions of taste could be traced back to their origins to reveal the causal relation between individual thought and the emotions triggered by initial stimuli. Such tracing, he argued, would allow one to distinguish between genuine qualities and mere incidental pleasures. It would in a sense be possible to eradicate prejudice and make aesthetic judgement more pure and grounded.

2 Troscianko, "Cognitive realism and memory in Proust's madeleine episode", 12

3 Lears, *Fables of Abundance. A Cultural History of Advertising in America*, 387

John Ruskin - who inhabited a world not far from Alison's and whom Proust revered - similarly traced associations between the symbolic, the religious, the social, and the material: from ornament and construction to national landscapes.

Ruskin was not alone in this. His contemporaries, the utilitarians - a dominant philosophical current in the early nineteenth century - asserted that associations could be traced between the individual and society. To conceive of the mind as associative was not a mere metaphor, but a model for understanding the relationship between self and world. Even Charles Darwin, inspired by aesthetics, traced the origins of character and expression to associations with the natural environment, focusing on those with evolutionary functions such as communication, child-rearing, and procreation. His nephew, Francis Galton, extended this lineage by developing statistical methods to trace associations from objects to ideas - transforming speculation into experimental science.

III

But Proust did not only attempt to capture a phenomenon which was discussed in the eighteenth or nineteenth century. It was very much a topic of his time. The book captures the "spirit" of *fin-de-siècle* culture, through a concept which was at the centre of academic thought and debate at the time, *In Search of Lost Time* was written - between 1909 and 1922.

In Proust's time, the associative mind came to be understood as a mechanism essential to creative thought - to art, symbolism, taste, style, character, and even the evolution of gesture. Only a few decades earlier, the concept had travelled from the British Isles to the Continent. A few years prior, in Leipzig, the notion of the associative mind had become the theoretical counterpart to the system of nerve cells composing the brain, and - perhaps more importantly - had become accessible through experimental research. The inner workings of the mind were no longer purely speculative but increasingly subject to empirical investigation. British associationism and German scientific Psychology, especially that of Wundt and Fechner were being introduced into French intellectual life, by the french psychologist Theodule Ribot.

This impetus led Sigmund Freud and Pierre Janet, in turn, to develop therapeutic and analytical methods for tracing associative processes within the psyche. Soon after, Gabriel Tarde and Émile Durkheim debated its implications for sociology, as associations began to be viewed not merely as markers of identity but as structures mediating the relationship between individual and collective consciousness. In Switzerland, Ferdinand de Saussure explored its relevance - the human impulse to associate - for a nascent science of signs: semiology. After all, it is through the sign that we associate and transmit meaning; it serves as the medium between the psychological and the social. In 1922 when Proust, as he wrote the last word to his novel, surrealism was beginning to form, and transposed ideas originating in science into art.⁴ The *Recherche* thus responds to a distinct intellectual current that traversed academic discourse at the turn of the century - a current whose relevance only deepened in a time of rapid transformation, marked by new technologies, new ideas, and new habits. Mind and society were changing together.

4 His correspondences and notes show a continued interest in Ruskin, the psychology of Ribot, the philosophy of Bergson and the social theories of Tarde. There is a large corpus which addresses Proust's translation of psychological theories for literary effect: Werner's Essay: "The Psychology of Marcel Proust", Jonah Lehrer's book *Proust was a Neuroscientist* and Deleuze has tried to show that Proust goes beyond the association of ideas in *Proust & Sign*.

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